

Column 1:
uORFs

Column 2:
uoORFs

Column 3:
intORFs

Column 4:
doORFs

Column 5:
dORFs

Type 0: No ambiguity. Specific roles of each ORF are known (no example)

Type 1: Neither ORF is affected (no example)

Type 2: Both refORF and ncORF are affected (example: ncORF12)

Type 3: Both refORF and ncORF are affected, and an additional line has only refORF affected (examples: ncORFs 1, 7, 8, and 13)

Type 4: Both refORF and ncORF are affected, and an additional line has only ncORF affected (no example)

Type 5: Only refORF is affected (examples: ncORFs 2, 4, 5, and 10)

Type 6: Only ncORF is affected (example: ncORF6)

Legend:

- RefORF
- NcORF
- UTR
- Insertion, deletion, or non-synonymous substitution
- Substitution that affects refORF only
- Substitution that affects ncORF only
- RNAi construct (or other PTGS tool) that affects both ORFs